

Simultaneous Estimation of Cholesterol and its Biodegradation Product Androsta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione

SHRIDHAR PATIL*, NAKUL PHASE, ANIRUDDHA SHUKLA and AJIT SRIVASTAVA

School of Life Sciences, Devi Ahilya Vishwavidyalaya, Vigyan Bhavan, Khandwa Road, Indore-452 001

Manuscript received 4 August 1992, revised 3 February 1993, accepted 19 February 1993

A spectrophotometric method for the estimation of cholesterol and androsta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione (ADD) applying two wavelength calculation method after recording the absorbance of respective chromogens formed in concentrated sulphuric acid at 315–370 and 390–420 nm is described. Estimation of residual cholesterol and ADD formed during cholesterol biotransformation by *Mycobacterium fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 is described.

Androsta-1,4-diene-3,17-dione (ADD) is a key intermediate used for the commercial manufacture of female sex hormones and their derivatives. Microbial cleavage of C-17 side-chain of cholesterol and phytosterols yield ADD¹. Separate methods are available for the estimation of ADD based on Zimmermann reaction² and of sterols based on Liebermann-Burchard reaction³.

The present communication reports a common method for the estimation of cholesterol and ADD in a binary mixture using two wavelength calculation method and its application to estimate these compounds during cholesterol side-chain cleavage by *Mycobacterium fortuitum* NRRL B-8153. The method is based on the observation that these compounds form characteristic chromogens in concentrated sulphuric acid.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of cholesterol and ADD chromogens formed in concentrated sulphuric acid after 40 min are presented in Fig. 1. Cholesterol and ADD chromogens showed absorption maxima (λ_1) at 315 and 390 nm respectively, and the corresponding wavelengths (λ_2) at 370 and 420 nm. The difference between the absorbance at 315 and 370 nm was found to be proportional to the amount of cholesterol irrespective of the amount of ADD in the binary mixture (Table 1) Similarly, the difference of ab-

sorbance at 390 and 420 nm was proportional to the amount of ADD alone. The absorbance differences at these wavelengths were proportional to amounts

Fig. 1. Overlay absorption spectra of (O) cholesterol and (●) ADD in conc. H₂SO₄ after 40 min.

of cholesterol and ADD present in any proportion in binary mixture and were in agreement with Beer's law in a concentration range 0–50 $\mu\text{g}/3$ ml.

From the straight-line curves for cholesterol and ADD obtained, the following equations were developed :

$$\text{Concentration of cholesterol } (\mu\text{g}) = 220.07 [A_{315} - A_{370}] + 0.804 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Concentration of ADD } (\mu\text{g}) = 207.19 [A_{390} - A_{420}] - 0.545 \quad (2)$$

TABLE 1 – ABSORBANCE DIFFERENCES OF VARIOUS PROPORTIONS OF CHOLESTEROL AND ADD CHROMOGENS FORMED IN CONCENTRATED SULPHURIC ACID AFTER 40 MIN TREATMENT

Concn $\mu\text{g}/3\text{ ml}$	ADD	Absorbance difference		Absorbance difference calculated for 1 μg compound % Error	
		$(A_{315} - A_{370})$	$(A_{390} - A_{420})$	Cholesterol	ADD
00	50	-0.003	0.238	-	0.004 8 (0.0)
10	40	0.043	0.198	0.004 3 (+4.4)	0.005 0 (-4.1)
20	30	0.082	0.153	0.004 1 (+8.8)	0.005 1 (-6.2)
30	20	0.130	0.101	0.004 3 (+4.4)	0.005 0 (-4.1)
40	10	0.178	0.050	0.004 4 (+2.2)	0.005 0 (-4.1)
50	00	0.227	-0.003	0.004 5 (0.0)	— —

Using the above equations, the utilisation of cholesterol and formation of ADD in the incubation medium by *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 was followed. The results of percentage utilisation of cholesterol and mole percentage formation of ADD are presented in Table 2. It is evident that about 89% cholesterol was utilised and 39% ADD was formed in the incubation medium after 216 h. *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 is a mutant bacterium blocked at 9α -hydroxylation of the steroid nucleus⁴. However, the mole percentage formation of ADD is much less than expected on the basis of cholesterol utilisation. It seems that 9α -hydroxylase activity is not completely blocked in this bacterium, thereby further breakdown of ADD occurs in the medium. The limitation of the method is that it can not be applied if cholesterol degradation product other than ADD is detected in the incubation medium by tlc analysis.

Experimental

Determination of λ_1 and λ_2 : Methanolic solutions of cholesterol and ADD (Sigma) containing 10 μg compound were vacuum-dried in separate tubes. The residue was dissolved in 98% sulphuric acid (A.R.) (3 ml) and kept in a boiling water-bath for 40 min. After cooling to room temperature, the absorption spectrum of the resulting chromogen and absorption maxima (λ_1) were recorded in the wavelength range 250–450 nm on a Shimadzu 160 A spectrophotometer. After overlaying the cholesterol and ADD chromogen spectra, λ_2 for each chromogen was determined which represented a wavelength at which one chromogen showed exactly the same absorbance as at the absorption maxima (λ_1) of the other chromogen⁵.

Preparation of standard curves : From a methan-

TABLE 2 – PERCENTAGE CONVERSION OF CHOLESTEROL TO ADD BY *M. Fortuitum* NRRL B-8153

Time h	Absorbance difference		Compound estimated in 50 ml medium mg		% Cholesterol utilisation	Mole % conversion to ADD
	$(A_{315} - A_{370})$	$(A_{390} - A_{420})$	Cholesterol	ADD		
00	0.222	0.002	24.80	0.062	0.80	0.30
48	0.169	0.013	19.80	1.070	23.40	5.30
96	0.153	0.024	17.20	2.210	30.60	12.10
144	0.118	0.035	13.38	3.400	46.00	18.70
168	0.068	0.065	8.00	6.400	67.70	35.20
216	0.021	0.072	2.71	7.180	89.10	39.50

olic stock solution of cholesterol ($100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), 0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 ml portions were pipetted in separate tubes and mixed respectively with 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1 and 0.0 ml aliquots of ADD ($100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The residue obtained after evaporation of methanol under reduced pressure, was dissolved in 98% sulphuric acid (3 ml). The tubes were placed in a boiling water-bath for 40 min and the absorbance difference at predetermined λ_1 and λ_2 for cholesterol and ADD chromogens, was recorded after cooling to room temperature.

Bioconversion of cholesterol : M. fortuitum NRRL B-8153 was grown in a medium containing (g dm^{-3}) yeast extract, 5.0; NH_4NO_3 , 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.25; K_2HPO_4 , 0.25; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.001; pH adjusted to 7.5, and was used for cholesterol to ADD bio-conversion. The medium (50 ml) dispensed in 250 ml erlenmeyer flask was inoculated with actively growing bacterial culture (1 ml) and incubated on gyratory incubator shaker (180 rpm, 25 mm eccentric throw) at $30 \pm 2^\circ$. After growing the culture for 72 h, cholesterol (25 mg) dissolved in dimethyl-formamide (0.2 ml) was aseptically added to the culture. The sample (1 ml) of the broth was periodically drawn and extracted with ethyl acetate (1 ml).

The extract was used for estimation and tlc after drying over sodium sulphate. Aliquots of ethyl acetate extract (0.1 ml) were transferred to separate tubes and dried under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in sulphuric acid and processed as above. The concentrations of the residual cholesterol and ADD formed in the medium was calculated using the equations developed.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from Department of Biotechnology, New Delhi, is thankfully acknowledged.

References

1. C. K. A. MARTIN, *Adv Appl Microbiol.*, 1977, **22**, 29; S. K. SRIVASTAVA, R. A. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. N. MATHUR, *J. Appl. Bacteriol.*, 1985, **59**, 399; S. B. MAHATO, S. BANERJEE and S. PODDER, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 7; P. G. M. HESSELINK, S. VAN VLIET, H. DE VRIES and B. WITHOLT, *Enzyme Microbial Technol.*, 1989, **11**, 398.
2. D. J. PONTIUS, *Anal Chem*, 1962, **34**, 168.
3. T. C. STADTMAN, "Methods in Enzymology", Academic, New York, 1957, Vol. III, p. 392.
4. M. G. WOVCHA, F. J. ANTOSZ, J. C. KNIGHT, L. A. KOMINEK and T. R. PYKE, *Biochim Biophys. Acta*, 1978, **531**, 308.
5. S. PATIL, A. SRIVASTAVA, A. SHUKLA and N. PHASE, *World J Microbiol Biotechnol.*, 1991, **7**, 626.

